

Maqam of Sidi Ibrahim Arriyahi مقام سيدي إبراهيم الرياحي

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Religious Place, Religious Place (fr), Sufi, Tunisia

Il est Abu Ishaq Sidi Ibrahim al-Riyahi en 1180 AH / 1766 CE, ou en l'an 1181 AH / 1767 à Tastur au nord ouest de Tunis. Grand Mufti en Tunisie sur l'école Maliki. En l'an 1255 AH / 1839 AD, il fut nommé le plus grand imam et prédicateur de la Grande Mosquée. Sidi Ibrahim al-Riahi était célèbre pour sa défense des opprimés du peuple. Il était un grand diplomate il a été envoyé au Maroc pour demander l'aide du roi du Maroc, Mawla Suleiman al-Idrisi, et à Constantinople pour servir de médiateur auprès du Sultan ottoman afin de supprimer une taxe qui avait été imposée au pays tunisien. Sidi Ibrahim al-Riyahi a été appelé le tueur de rois à cause de ce qu'il avait l'habitude de faire pour affronter l'oppression des dirigeants et pour sa supplication à laquelle Dieu a répondu contre chaque oppresseur. La zawiya de Sidi Ibrahim al-Riyahi a été construite sur ordre du Bey, Ahmed Bey, et a été achevée sous le règne d'al-Sadiq Bey, qui a construit la célèbre madrasa, le collège al-Sadiqiyya. Sur le côté droit, il y a une grande salle couverte d'un dôme, qui est le lieu désigné pour les réunions rituelles spirituelles ou la Hadrat, qui rassemble tous les vendredis les membres de la Tariqa Tijaniyya. Cette coupole portée sur des troncs est l'une des perles de l'architecture hispano-marocaine, des artisans ont été spécialement amenés du Maroc pour graver et sculpter le gypse. Le sanctuaire du marabout est situé à l'intérieur d'une petite salle en face du mihrab. Au-dessus de la plate-forme, le sarcophage est enveloppé de tissus de soie aux couleurs vives.

Date Range: 1878 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Tunis medina

Region tags: North Africa, Tunisia

The maqam is located in the Zawiyya (Zaouia) of Sidi Ibrahim Riahi in the Tunis medina.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Djaziri, Tahar, La régence de Tunis d'après l'action et les œuvres de Sidi Brahim al-Riahi (1750-1850), Thèse de doctorat en Histoire, Sous la direction de Dominique Chevallier, Paris 4, 1996.
- Source 2: 1978, إلياس, محمود, المرزوقي, رياض, إبراهيم الرياحي مفكرا وأديبا، الجامعة التونسية. تونس،
- Source 3: ابن أبي الصيف، إتخاف أهل الزّمان بملوك تونس وعهد الأمان، الدار العربية للكتاب، 1999، ص 73-82

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://tidjaniya.com/fr/sidi-ibrahim-riyahi-qu-allah-l-agree/>
- Source 1 Description: A brief introduction to Sheikh Ibrahim Al-Riyahi with a translation of part of a letter sent by Sheikh Ahmed Al-Tijani to Sheikh Ibrahim Al-Riyahi
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.leaders.com.tn/article/22694-un-oulema-sunnite-exemplaire-sidi-brahim-riahi-1766-1850>
- Source 2 Description: Introducing Sheikh Ibrahim Riahi and his value in the religious and general history of Tunisia
- Source 3 URL: https://data.bnf.fr/fr/14651143/ibrahim_ibn__abd_al-qadir_al-_riyah_i/
- Source 3 Description: A site belonging to the French National Library, which contains a detailed introductory sheet of Sheikh Ibrahim Al-Riyah with a number of similar sites in other languages.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Notes: This site has undergone a number of restorations and repairs over time

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: Maqam Ibrahim Al-Riyahi is located in the heart of the old city. On the road to Al-Zaytouna Mosque

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

Notes: Le lieu est un mélange de structure, c'est le type de "maison" arabe classique, avec une entrée et un haule, 3 grandes chambre, l'une d'elle est consacrée à la prière, et au fond de cette chambre on trouve le tombeau du Cheikh Ibrahim Arriyahi

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Le Maqam est caractérisé par dôme avec des caractères pertinentes.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Mais sans toucher à sa structure de base qui est la place du Tombeau et la chambre de la prière

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: Ma réponse est non malgré que les autorités ont fait des réparations

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: La communication avec Dieu ne veut pas dire parler avec un médium, Le Dhikr pour les Tijanis, avec la prière pour tout musulman, et pour plusieurs religions, est une sorte de dialogue avec le Créateur

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: C'est Dieu le Tout puissant

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Notes: Oui, c'est Ahmad Bey qui a ordonné le début de la construction de la Zaouia, et c'est à l'époque de Sadiq Bey qu'on a finit de la construire

Reference: المنظمة العربية للتربية والثقافة والعلوم. "زاوية سيدي إبراهيم الرياحي لمحة تاريخية".

<http://188.165.237.85/medinatunis/>, n.d.. <http://188.165.237.85/medinatunis/index.php/ar/mosquees-et-zaouias-2/zaouia-sidi-ibrahim-riahi>.

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Reference: Hatem, Karoui. "Le Cheikh Sidi Brahim Riahi (1767-1850), Un Adversaire Farouche Du Wahhabisme". <https://www.espacemanager.com/>, n.d.. <https://www.espacemanager.com/le-cheikh-sidi-brahim-riahi-1767-1850-un-adversaire-farouche-du-wahhabisme.html>.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Reference: "سفارات الشيخ الرياحي". Edited by 30 "الساحلي, حمادي". *المطبعة الرسمية. حوليات الجامعة التونسية* no. 2 (n.d.). <https://doi.org/>غير موجود.

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Le Bey de La Tunisie a voulu faire un faveur à Sidi Ibrahim Arriyahi

Notes: Although Sidi Ibrahim al-Riyahi was not Bey's man court he was strong in facing Bey and his retinue, and they were afraid of him and that he would curse them, he was known among them as the killer of the beys. يقول كاتب كتاب "تعطير النواحي": "وكان المشير المذكور يقول لم يقتل والدي غير دعاء سيدي إبراهيم ولذلك كان يتحامي جانبه كثيرا" ص 139

Reference: تونس: المكتبة. Vol. 2. جامع الزيتونة Edited by علي الرياحي, عمر بن محمد. تعطير النواحي العتيقة, n.d..

<https://zaouiatijania.ovh/livre/TaatirNawahiSidilbrahimRiahiRadhyaAllahouAnhou.pdf>.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: We have to distinguish between those who built the Zaouia and those who are responsible for covering its needs. The Bey built the zawiya he was not a Tijani, The financing of the Zaouia comes from the gifts of the Tijanies

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: For politicians, merchants, or some women (single or childless), visiting Zawyet Sidi Ibrahim has purposes other than worship.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Reference: Site plurielle. "Zaouia-sidi-brahim-riahi". <https://plurielle.tn>, n.d.. <https://plurielle.tn/pro/tunis/zaouia-sidi-brahim-riahi/>.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: La Zaouia est une entité complète ses composantes sont liées l'une à l'autre

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 30

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Marbre, fer, acier

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Les portes, les mosaïques, les vitres des fenêtres, Ornements des murs...

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Reference: Kammoun, Zaher. "Zaouia Sidi Brahim Riahi". <http://zaherkammoun.com/>, n.d..
<http://zaherkammoun.com/2016/02/06/zaouia-sidi-brahim-riahi/>.

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Une décoration simple qui ressemble à la décoration des maisons des riches

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Une décoration assez complexe riche de figures géométrique et de couleurs

Reference: Zaher, Kammoun. "Zaouïa Sidi Brahim Riahi *زاوية سيدي ابراهيم الرباحي*". <https://zaherkammoun.com>, n.d.. <https://zaherkammoun.com/gallery/zaouia-sidi-brahim-riahi/>.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: On trouve de la décoration attachée au bâtiment, et de la décoration mobile

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: malgré que toutes les réponses sont non. je tiens à insister qu'il y a présence du surnaturel qui consiste dans les tableaux dans lesquels est écrit des versés du Coran ou des vers de poésie dites par le Cheikh Sidi Ibrahim lui-même, ou le tableau qui représente le tombeau du Cheikh Sidi Ahmad Tijani. tous ces tableaux représentent la présence du divin, du surnaturel dans le Maqam.

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

Notes: Si par représenté on vise des images, des statuettes, des icones ou des symboles alors la réponse est non. Mais le tombeau du Cheikh est lui même un symbole de présence surnaturelle.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Ce qui attire l'attention c'est la similitude presque complète entre l'ornement du Maqam est les maisons des riches notables de la régence de Tunis

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Ce ne sont pas des images ni même des photos mais des calligraphies. Des tableaux ou il est écrits des ré citations du Saint Coran

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: Des vers tirés parfois du Diwan du Cheikh lui même

–Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Il faut prêter attention aux couleurs dominantes qui sont le vert et le rouge et le bleu

Notes: Le symbolisme du vert est mélioratif (verdure, paradis, pureté de l'âme...) le rouge est certainement le diable le feu mais aussi le rare surtout dans le domaine du soufisme (on parle du Soufre rouge qui est l'un des surnoms d'Ibn Arabi l'imminent mystique musulman), le bleu enfin est le symbole du ciel et de la mer profonde, la mer est le symbole de la connaissance du mystique.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Le mélange des couleurs peut être significatif

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Les inscriptions incitent à la dévotion et à la bonté

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Des inscriptions concernant le Wird et La Jawharat Kamal

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: Le Mehrab, là où le Imam se tient debout pour commencer la prière est un signe, par sa forme géométrique, de l'au-delà.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Quelques vers de poésie font rappeler quelques événements de la vie du Cheikh Ibrahim Riahi

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Le Maqam au début, c'est à dire dans la vie du Cheikh, était le Khalwa du Cheikh bâti par le bey (ou par le cheikh lui même). c'est pourquoi on trouve des parties de la zawiya destinée à préparer les repas pour les fouqarats et les invités.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Avec cette remarque que c'est Dieu Unique et non pas des dieux. Si on considère les anges comme des divinités du ciel alors on peut dire oui pour leurs présence mais ce n'est pas une présence permanente

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Notes: Une légende nous parle d'une visite des Djinn submergés du puits ont eu une brève conversation avec le Cheikh

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Notes: Oui c'est le lien de dévotion et de soumission

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: C'est Dieu et ses anges, ce ne sont pas une multitude de divinités

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Ils sont vus par quelque personnes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Ils sont ressentis par quelques personnes

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: La réponse est oui mais avec ce détail: la communication n'est pas volontère c'est à dire il n'y a pas une personne qui communique comme le fait un prophète (dans le sens non musulman). la communication est soudaine, se rapporte à la volonté de l'au-delà et non pas de l'homme. voir 311 جواهر المعاني، ص

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Ces pratiques sont très mal vues par les responsables du Maqam et par les Tijanis de Tunis en général

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: la communication n'est pas liée à la spécialisation dans le domaine religieux mais au degrés de la dévotion, de la "simplicité" et la "propreté" de l'esprit

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Par quelques personnes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Par quelques personnes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Ces pratiques sont très mal vu par les responsables du Maqam et des Tijanis en général

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: La communication n'est pas liée à la spécialisation dans le domaine religieux mais à l'état de l'esprit et de l'âme (Ahwal).

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: L'intérêt au sex n'est pas lié à l'acte mais on demande parfois de l'aide dans la vie de couple ou la vie sexuelle

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Les préoccupations des êtres supérieurs à cet égard ne sont pas similaires à certains sanctuaires non islamiques. Malgré la croyance qu'ils existent dans le Maqam et qu'ils se soucient de ce qui s'y passe, ils n'interfèrent en rien.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

Notes: pas forcemant

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Les offrandes et les cadeaux sont surtout de l'argent pour que le Maqam peut survivre

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– No

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Il y a une famille, composé d'ordinaire des petits fils du Cheikh, qui s'occupe de l'entretien du Maqam

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

↳ Divination through human communication:

– Yes

Notes: La communication et l'interprétation se font principalement par question et réponse : quelqu'un demande la signification de quelque chose qu'il a vu ou qui s'est produit dans son esprit et demande son interprétation au cheikh ou à l'un de ceux en qui le questionneur a confiance.

- ↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:
 - No
- ↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:
 - No
- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:
 - No
- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:
 - No
- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:
 - No
- ↳ Is sex-deprivation required:
 - No
- ↳ Are intoxicants required:
 - No
- ↳ Physical ordeal required:
 - No
- ↳ Divination through animal-behavior:
 - No
- ↳ Divination through non-living material:
 - Other [specify in comments]
Notes: Par le plomb jeté à l'esau après être chauffé. mais ces pratiques ne sont plus pratiquées à nos jours, surtout que les responsables du Maqam ne les acceptent pas
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: L'ame du Cheikh (Tijani) et de ses compagnons, notamment Le Khalifa Cheikh Ibrahim Riahi, sont présente surtout lors du dhikr

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– Yes

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Peut-être par des récitaions coranique ou du dhikr

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Les taches dans le Maqam sont divisées en somme en deux: taches de prière et dhikr les hommes de la famille Riyahi sont responsables de cette tache. les femmes de la même famille ou d'une famille proche sont responsables du ménage quotidien, Recevoir les invités et s'occuper des femmes qui viennent visiter le Dharih (ضريح)

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Le ministère des affaires religieuses et le ministère des affaires culturelles

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: Surout au Ramadhan

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: très rarement on assiste à une cérémonie de circoncision, ou de déclaration de mariage

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

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